

ELECTRIFICATION PLANNING FOR ZAMBIA USING OPEN-SOURCE SPATIAL ELECTRIFICATION TOOL (OnSSET)

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ZAMBIA

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ESMAP	Energy Sector Management Assistance Program
GEP	Global Electrification Platform
GIS	Geographic Information System
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPPs	Independent Power Producers
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
MV	Medium Voltage
OnSSET	Open-Source Spatial Electrification
PV	Photovoltaic
QGIS	Quantum Geographic Information System
SHS	Solar Home Systems

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This report is the outcome of a three-week training, which began with an online session from 19th to 23rd January 2026, followed by an in-person session from 26th January to 6th February 2026, held at the University of Cape Town. The training was organized and provided by Climate Compatible Growth (CCG), International Center for Theoretical Physics (ICTP), World Bank Group, Sustainable Energy for All, Kartoza, KTH, World Resources Institute, OpTIMUS Community, FCDO, 2050 Pathways Platform, and IAEA.

Special appreciation goes to the World Bank for its generous support, which made my participation in this programme possible. I also extend sincere thanks to the programme organizers, Climate Compatible Growth (CCG), for the effective coordination and delivery of the training.

Finally, we extend our heartfelt gratitude to the trainers Stella Chelangat Mutai and Nicky Middleton for their exceptional guidance and the invaluable knowledge they shared throughout the programme.

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the outcomes of a technical training programme on geospatial electrification modelling, with a focus on tools such as QGIS and OnSSET to support integrated electrification planning. The training enabled participants to visualise spatial disparities in electricity access, optimise investment decisions, and align electrification strategies with national development goals.

The competencies acquired through the programme are expected to enhance participants' ability to undertake spatial data analysis, support data-driven policy formulation, and contribute effectively to sustainable energy access planning. A key emphasis of the training was the development of evidence-based, least-cost electrification scenarios to inform national energy planning processes.

These scenarios were developed in close alignment with Zambia's policy priorities, as articulated in Vision 2030, the National Energy Policy (2019), and the Zambia Energy Compact (2024).

Electrification Pathways by 2030

The following electrification scenarios were considered towards achieving universal access to electricity by 2030:

i. **Scenario 1 – Full Grid Expansion**

Universal electricity access is achieved by 2030 through comprehensive grid extension and nationwide network expansion.

ii. **Scenario 2 – Off-Grid Priority**

Universal electricity access is achieved by 2030, driven primarily by least-cost off-grid solutions, with grid-based connections limited to a maximum of 100,000 annually.

The scenarios were developed using demographic assumptions for 2024 as the base year, with an estimated population of 20.8 million. A population growth rate of 3.1% was applied to project a population of approximately 25 million by 2030, which was set as the target year. Additional assumptions included an urbanisation rate of 40%, an average urban household size of four (4), and an average rural household size of five (5).

The results indicate that achieving universal access to electricity by 2030 will require approximately 3 million new connections, at an estimated total

investment cost of USD 1.45 billion under Scenario 1 and USD 1.37 billion under Scenario 2. A comparison of the two scenarios shows that similar numbers of connections are expected from grid densification and solar mini grids in both cases. However, the scenarios differ in their technology priorities: Scenario 1 places greater emphasis on grid extension, while Scenario 2 prioritises a higher share of connections through solar home systems. Furthermore, Scenario 1 is projected to result in higher emissions, with 78.83 tCO₂, compared to 76.87 tCO₂ under Scenario 2.

Recommendations

Scenario 1 is recommended for implementation. Although it entails slightly higher investment costs and emissions than Scenario 2, it delivers Tier 4 levels of electricity access, thereby offering greater socio-economic and productive-use benefits to consumers. Consequently, Scenario 1, which places greater emphasis on grid extension over solar home systems, is recommended as the preferred electrification pathway for Zambia.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

As of 2022, Zambia's population is estimated at approximately 19.6 million, growing at an annual rate of 3.1%. The average household size is four (4) persons in urban areas and five (5) persons in rural areas. Based on these trends, the population is projected to reach around 25 million by 2030. Despite this growth, a significant proportion of the population, particularly in rural areas, remains underserved in terms of electricity access.

Zambia's energy sector plays a critical role in supporting economic growth, particularly in key sectors such as mining, agriculture, and manufacturing. The country's power system is predominantly hydropower-based, with an installed generation capacity of approximately 3,965.8 MW and an average peak demand of about 2,450.7 MW. In line with Vision 2030, Zambia aims to achieve universal access to clean, reliable, and affordable energy by 2030.

Currently, national electricity access stands at approximately 53.6%, with grid-based access accounting for 34% and off-grid solutions contributing 19.6%. A pronounced disparity exists between urban and rural areas, where access levels are approximately 80.3% and 34%, respectively.

Low energy access remains a significant challenge in Zambia, with 46.4% of the population lacking access to electricity. The country's heavy dependence on hydropower generation further exposes the energy sector to climate change-related risks, particularly variability in rainfall patterns. In addition, high electricity connection costs continue to limit access, especially in rural areas, leaving many communities unconnected to the national grid.

To address these challenges, the Government has set a target to achieve universal electricity access by 2030 through a combination of grid and off-grid solutions. In addition, it aims to increase the share of non-hydropower renewable energy in the national energy mix from 3% to 33% by 2030, while expanding annual grid connections from approximately 60,000 in 2022 to 120,000 by 2030, in line with the country's long-term national development and energy policies.

1.2 Purpose and Scope

This report analyses Zambia’s electrification strategy, evaluating alternative pathways for achieving universal electricity access by 2030. It utilises the OnSSET model to identify the most effective technology mix, taking into account existing grid infrastructure, available energy resources, and settlement distribution. The report further presents two electrification scenarios developed during the EMP-A 2026 training. The modelling results provide critical evidence to support national energy planning and inform policy formulation.

1.3 Aims and Objectives

- i. To identify and evaluate the most cost-effective and sustainable electrification pathway for achieving universal access (100%) to energy services by 2030.
- ii. Specifically, assess alternative electrification pathways (grid extension, mini-grids, and stand-alone systems).
- iii. Determine the least-cost combination of technologies that deliver clean, reliable and affordable energy.
- iv. Aligned with national development plans, energy policies, and climate commitments.

1.4 Connection to Zambia’s M300 Initiative

This report contributes to the Mission 300 (M300) initiative, led by the African Development Bank and the World Bank, in collaboration with multiple partners, which aims to provide electricity access to 300 million people by 2030. It further strengthens national capacity for integrated, data-driven energy planning, supporting the development of more efficient and effective electrification strategies.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Modelling Tool Implemented

OnSSET was used as the primary modelling tool during the training, enabling the evaluation of electrification pathways through the simulation of grid densification, grid extensions, mini-grids, and solar home systems, based on population distribution, demand levels, resource availability, and existing infrastructure. QGIS was employed for spatial data processing and visualisation, while OnSSET was executed in a Jupyter environment within

Anaconda. The model allows for the integration of multiple parameters including costs, population density, and grid infrastructure to identify the least-cost and most viable electrification pathways.

2.2 Data Sources

Data for the modelling process was sourced from various reliable platforms, including:

- i. Demographics: Zambia Statistics Agency
- ii. Grid Infrastructure: Rural Electrification Authority
- iii. Energy Statistics: Ministry of Energy
- iv. GIS Base Maps: OpenStreetMap
- v. Solar PV and Wind Data: ESMAP
- vi. Demand Clusters: ESMAP

2.3 Data Preparation

Prior to analysis, data underwent several preparation steps, including:

- **Data Cleaning:** Ensuring data accuracy through the identification and removal of inconsistencies and errors.
- **Geospatial Alignment:** Standardising all datasets to a common coordinate reference system (WGS 84, EPSG:4326) to enable accurate spatial analysis.
- **Datasets Integration:** Consolidating demographic, geographic, and economic datasets into a unified database to support comprehensive and consistent modelling.

2.4 Assumptions

The following assumptions were considered in the modelling process:

- Start year: 2024
- Start year population: 20.8 million
- Target year: 2030
- Target year population: 25 million
- Annual growth rate: 3.1%
- Urban ratio: 40%
- Target year access rate: 100%
- Minimum number of HH for minigrid: 100
- Minigrid radius: 1km
- MV network extension: 50km
- Carbon emission factor: 200 tCO₂

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- Demand targets
 - ✓ Tier 1 - Low rural (20 kwh)
 - ✓ Tier 2 - High rural (73 kwh)
 - ✓ Tier 4 – Urban (1,241 kwh)

2.5 Modelled Scenarios

2.5.1 Scenario 1 – Full Grid Expansion:

This scenario assumes that universal electricity access is achieved by 2030 through extensive grid development and nationwide network expansion. It represents an optimal-case scenario, in which the Government is assumed to have no financial constraints on electrification investments. The scenario applies OnSSET’s automated parameter settings to identify the least-cost electrification technologies across the country.

Key inputs include a base year of 2024, calibrated to reflect current electricity access levels, and a target of 100% access by 2030. Population projections for 2030 are based on an urbanisation rate of 40%, with an average household size of 4.6 persons in urban areas and 5 persons in rural areas. No limits are imposed on the number of grid connections, allowing grid expansion wherever it is deemed economically and technically viable.

2.5.1 Scenario 2 – Off-Grid Priority:

Universal electricity access by 2030 under this scenario is achieved primarily through least-cost off-grid solutions, with annual grid connections capped at 100,000. The scenario reflects Zambia’s strong potential for distributed renewable energy, particularly in rural and remote areas. It also accounts for the widespread use of solar home systems, the predominance of rural settlements, and declining global PV costs. Accordingly, a top-down access approach incorporating Tier 4, Tier 2, and Tier 1 service levels, alongside limited grid expansion, was applied.

3.RESULTS

3.1. Scenario 1: Full Grid Expansion

The results of scenario 1 are as presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Results of Scenario 1

Technology	Population 2030	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment 2030 (million USD)	Emissions 2030 (tCO2)
Grid densification	13,214,455	459,104	99.57	598.47	73.52
Grid extension	768,488	165,899	7.85	172.42	5.31
SHS	10,895,812	2,362,957	47.38	620.4	0
Solar mini grid	121,244	16,260	14.75	56.9	0
Total	24,999,999	3,004,220	169.55	1,448.19	78.83

The map below illustrates the structures electrified using different technology options for scenario 1.

Figure 1: Scenario 1 Map Layout

The analysis revealed that universal access will be achieved through grid densification, grid extension, solar mini grids and solar home systems, targeting 3,004,220 connections. The estimated total investment cost for this scenario is approximately USD 1.448 billion, with a total additional capacity of 169 MW expected by 2030.

3.2. Scenario 2: Off-Grid Priority

The results for Scenario 2 are as presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Results of Scenario 2

Technology	Population 2030	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment 2030 (million USD)	Emissions 2030 (tCO2)
Grid densification	13,214,455	459,104	99.57	598.47	73.52
Grid extension	67,410	13,482	4.49	17.33	3.35
SHS	11,596,889	2,515,374	52.82	700.72	0
Solar mini grid	121,244	16,260	14.75	56.9	0
Total	24,999,999	3,004,220	171.68	1,373.42	76.87

The map below illustrates the structures electrified using different technology options for scenario 2.

Figure 2: Scenario 2 Map Layout

Like Scenario 1, the analysis further revealed that universal access will be achieved through grid densification, grid extension, solar mini grids and solar home systems, targeting 3,004,220 connections. However, the estimated total investment cost for scenario 2 is approximately USD 1.373 billion, with a total additional capacity of 171 MW expected by 2030.

3.3. Comparison of Scenarios

The comparison of the 2 scenarios is as presented in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Scenario Comparison

Description	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
New Connections	3,004,220	3,004,220
Additional Capacity (MW)	169.95	171.68
Investment (Million USD)	1,448.19	1,373.42
Emissions (tCO₂)	78.83	76.87
Electrification Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grid Densification • Grid Extension • Solar Home Systems • Solar Mini grids 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grid Densification • Grid Extension • Solar Home Systems • Solar Mini grids

The chart below shows scenario connection comparison per technology.

Figure 3: Scenario Connection Comparison

- **Cost:** Scenario 2 is notably more affordable, with a total investment of \$1.373 billion compared to \$1.448 billion in Scenario 1.
- **Emissions:** Scenario 1 is projected to result in higher emissions, with 78.83 tCO₂, compared to 76.87 tCO₂ under Scenario 2.
- **Technology Mix:** Both scenarios rely primarily on grid densification, with solar home systems (SHS) and solar PV mini grids providing an equal number of connections in each case. However, Scenario 1 places greater emphasis on grid extension, while Scenario 2 prioritises a higher number of solar home system connections.

4.0 Discussion and Recommendation

Based on the analysis, achieving universal access to electricity by 2030 will require a diversified mix of technologies. Scenario 1 is well suited for public sector investment, as it prioritizes a higher number of grid extension projects. Scenario 2, which incorporates an increased share of connections through solar home systems, is more attractive for private sector participation.

It is Zambia's policy to electrify settlements that are in proximity to the grid through grid extension. Therefore, scenario 1 emerges as the most effective pathway for achieving universal access, as it strategically proposes grid extensions in areas where demand clusters are close to existing infrastructure, thereby making grid expansion both economically and technically viable. Despite having a higher investment cost and more emissions expected, Scenario 1 offers:

- i. Increased Tier 4 level of access
- ii. More sustainable technology
- iii. Increased socio-economic activities and
- iv. Opportunity for Productive use of energy.

4.1. Limitations

- i. Demand clusters do not include loads from social institutions such as schools and health facilities.
- ii. Solar homes systems do not contribute to current access levels during the modelling process.
- iii. No routing algorithm to determine the network routes for LV network
- iv. Model does not incorporate attributes for the proposed MV lines.

4.2. Future Research Areas

- i. Integration of an attribute allocation algorithm to systematically assign technical parameters to model outputs.
- ii. Development of a routing algorithm to optimise network layouts for recommended off-grid systems.
- iii. Incorporation of solar home systems (SHS) into the model to contribute to electricity access rates within the overall modelling framework.

4. CONCLUSION

The modelling of various electrification scenarios using OnSSET has significantly strengthened our capacity for spatial electrification planning in Zambia. The results provide valuable insights into the trade-offs among cost, coverage, and technology mix when expanding electricity access.

Additionally, the modelling results will play a vital role in policy formulation and electrification planning towards achieving universal access by 2030.

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